

Female Authorship Has Increased in Computer and Information Sciences, but Further Growth in Gender Representation is Still Needed

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ABSTRACT

Computer science and information science and technology fields have long struggled to increase gender representation. The lack of female/women authors and researchers in these fields has been noted in several studies in past decades. A recent analysis of ten top computer and information science journals indicates that efforts to increase female participation in computer science and information science research fields may have had some effect, as representation of female authors has grown by a significant margin in the past decade. However, there remains a substantial gulf between the number of female authors in these fields compared the male authors.

KEYWORDS

Authorship; Female Authors; Women; Gender; Publication Trends

INTRODUCTION

Gender representation in the computer and information sciences has historically favored males over females by a substantial margin (Lund & Shamsi, 2021; Wang et al., 2021). Only in recent decades has the percentage of female computer and information science students begun to experience gains, and this is not yet well reflected in the literature (Beyer et al., 2003; Wagner, 2016). There are some recent indications, however, that representation of female authors in top scholarly journals in different disciplines is improving throughout the 2010s (Shamsi et al., 2022; Trepte & Loths, 2020). This study evaluates whether these trends have also emerged among select top computer science and information science journals. It further addresses the question, are top computer science journals – relating to the study of computer technology and its applications (e.g., *Communication of the Association for Computing Machinery*) – or top information science journals – relating to the study of information collection, storage, retrieval, and use (e.g., *Journal of Association for Information Science and Technology*) – growing faster in representation of female authors?

METHODS

Authorship data for this study was procured from the Web of Science database. Ten top computer and information science journals were selected based on Impact Factor and relevance to discipline. Seven journals were more associated with computer science - *ACM Computing Surveys*, *Communications of the ACM*, *IEEE Communications Surveys and Tutorials*, *IEEE Transactions on Evolutionary Computation*, *IEEE Transactions on Neural Networks and Learning Systems*, *IEEE Transactions on Cybernetics*, and *Information Fusion* - and three were more associated with information science – *the Journal of the Association for Information Science and Technology*, *Information Processing and Management*, and *Journal of Information Science*. Author gender was determined using a simple algorithmic technique. Baseline data was collected from the United States' Social Security Administration (<https://www.ssa.gov/oact/babynames/limits.html>) and other relevant repositories on GitHub and other sources. The data needed to include three fields: name, gender, and frequency. Once the gender was assigned for each author name for the ten journals, several analyses were performed, including trend across all ten journals over time, and comparison of trends for each journal.

RESULTS

Figure 1 displays two charts, where the left chart displays the overall trend in male and female authors in all computer and information science journals studied over the 2012 – 2021 time period, and the right chart displays the trend for two particularly prominent journals in the computer science and information science areas: *Communications of the Association for Computing Machinery (ACM)* and the *Journal of the Association for Information Science and Technology (JASIS&T)*. The charts illustrate the growth of female authorship in computer and information sciences in the past decade. Female authorship nearly doubled. However, the total female authorship, even in the best year, barely reached one-fourth of the total male authorship.

In two top journals, one associated more with “computer science” and the other with “information science,” there is evidence of a sizeable increase in female authorship. The growth for *JASIS&T* was modest, as it started the decade already having relatively good female authorship compared to other computer science journal. The growth of the *Communications of the ACM* is more dramatic, with the proportion of female authors increases over two-fold in the course of a single decade. This difference is representative of all of computer science and information science journals studied. Information science journals started with higher representation and did not see much change over the past decade, while computer science journals started with very low representation and then grew over the course of the decade.

DISCUSSION

The growth of female authorship is an important development, as publication efforts are generally indicative of growth in representation in doctoral programs and faculty at research universities. Several studies suggest that this gender growth is occurring at the doctoral student and faculty recruitment levels (U.S. Department of Labor, 2022; Way et al., 2016). This is a notable turnaround, as the percentage of females in the computer and information sciences at the end of the 20th century was not only low, but was *decreasing*, with retention of young women in university programs being particularly poor (Cohoon, 2001). Efforts to promote women in computing appears to have had a positive effect on multiple fronts (Cheong et al., 2021).

Although the recent growth trends are new and not evident in the prior five-decade-plus of many of these computer science journals, it is worthwhile to examine, if the observed growth trends continued, if and when equitable representation, or gender parity, would be attained within the computer and information sciences. If we use the trend from 2012 to 2021, which averaged a 5% growth rate, then a 50-50 split of male and female authors could be attained by 2039. If an average growth rate of 3% was used (the average growth since 1960), then equitable representation could be attained by 2050. However, it is again important to note that these are limited trends, and prior history of these journals would indicate much slower growth (about 1 – 2% per year if the years 2012 to 2021 are removed from the data). It is worth noting that Wang et al. (2021), using a more expansive set of computer science articles, predicted that gender equity in computer sciences would not be attained until after 2100; this more expansive dataset, though, would be less able to reflect recent trends in the past decade.

CONCLUSION

This study illustrates meaningful and sustained, yet small and slow, growth in female authorship in the computer and information sciences. At the start of the 2010s, information science-leaning journals held an advantage in female authorship percentage; however, this gap has closed for many of the leading computer science journals in recent years. Journals with a lengthy history tend to have experienced this growth in the 2010s, whereas newer journals already held higher percentages of female authors. While these trends are a positive sign for gender representation in these disciplines and affiliated professions, significant disparities persist that must continue to be addressed. If gains over the past decade were continued, it is possible that equitable representation in these disciplines could be attained by 2050.

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